

Applications of Data Science Techniques in Medico-Statistics: Analyzing Insulin Resistance and Metabolic Markers in pregnant Women

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the association between metabolic parameters and insulin resistance using statistical modeling techniques. A cross-sectional analysis was conducted on 100 pregnant women attending the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology at Malla Reddy Narayana Multispeciality Hospital, Suraram, Hyderabad, to assess relationships between BMI, fasting glucose, fasting insulin and HOMA-IR. Pearson's correlation and multiple linear regression analysis were performed. Fasting insulin showed a strong positive correlation with HOMA-IR ($r=0.961, p<0.001$), while fasting glucose showed a moderate correlation ($r=0.389, p=0.005$). Regression analysis revealed fasting insulin as the strongest predictor of insulin resistance. The study demonstrates how statistical tools, including R programming can be applied in analyzing clinical parameters to understand metabolic conditions.

KEYWORDS

Insulin Resistance, HOMA-IR, Fasting Insulin, Fasting Glucose, Body Mass Index, Vitamin D, R Programming, Data Science Techniques.

INTRODUCTION

Insulin resistance is a common metabolic condition where the body's cells become less responsive to insulin. It plays a major role in the development of type-II diabetes, obesity, and several reproductive and metabolic disorders (Matthews et al., 1985). When the body is unable to absorb glucose efficiently, the pancreas compensates by producing more insulin, which leads to long-term health issues (Kim et al., 2023).

Identifying insulin resistance early is important in preventing further complications. Various clinical parameters such as fasting glucose, fasting insulin, HOMA-IR (Homeostatic Model Assessment of Insulin Resistance), BMI, waist circumference, hip circumference, and waist-hip ratio are used to assess insulin resistance (Matthews et al., 1985; Rabari et al., 2022).

This study was conducted in the Obstetrics and Gynecology (OBGY) department and involved analysis of clinical and biochemical data of pregnant women to evaluate metabolic parameters associated with insulin resistance (Najmunnissa et al., 2024).

Recent studies have emphasized the predictive value of fasting glucose and insulin levels in detecting insulin resistance during pregnancy. Kim et al. (2023) reported a strong link between HOMA-IR and diabetes risk, while Huang et al. (2022) compared linear regression and machine learning in glucose prediction. International findings also support early metabolic screening to improve pregnancy outcomes (Smith et al., 2024; WHO, 2021), highlighting the growing role of data science in antenatal care.

From a statistical point of view, identifying patterns and relationships among clinical variables helps in early risk assessment and data-driven decision-making (Altman, 1991; James et al., 2013). This study applies statistical tools such as descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and multiple linear regression to determine significant predictors of insulin resistance (Kuhn & Johnson, 2013; Breiman, 2001).

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

Aim:

To apply data science techniques to analyze the relationship between metabolic indicators and insulin resistance using R Programming.

Objectives:

- i) To assess the Correlation between BMI, Fasting glucose, Fasting insulin and waist-hip ratio with HOMA-IR.
- ii) To perform multiple linear regression analysis to identify significant predictors of insulin resistance.
- iii) To visualize the relationships and statistical outputs using R programming
- iv) To demonstrate the application of data science tools in medico-statistical research.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design and Setting: This is a cross-sectional analytical study conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at Malla Reddy Narayana Multispeciality Hospital, Suraram, Hyderabad. A total of 100 pregnant women were included using convenience sampling.

Sample size justification:

The required sample size was calculated using the formula for correlation studies:

$$n = \left(\frac{Z_{1-\alpha/2} + Z_{1-\beta}}{(0.5) \ln \left(\frac{1+r}{1-r} \right)} \right)^2 + 3$$

Assuming a 95% confidence level ($Z=1.96$), 80% power ($Z=0.84$) and a moderate correlation of $r=0.3$ (as observed in pilot data, based on Cohen's classification of effect sizes), we proceed with the calculation:

$$\ln\left(\frac{1+0.3}{1-0.3}\right) = \ln(1.857) = 0.619$$

$$n = \left(\frac{2.8}{0.5 * 0.619}\right)^2 + 3 = (9.05)^2 + 3 = 85$$

Adding 10% to account for non-response and missing data, the adjusted sample size was 94, which was rounded to 100 for convenience. This ensures sufficient statistical power to detect meaningful associations.

The objective was to explore the relationship between anthropometric and biochemical parameters and insulin resistance.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a pre-structured proforma. The variables included:

Demographics: Name, Age

Anthropometric measurements: Height, Weight, Waist circumference, Hip circumference

Derived indices: Body Mass Index (BMI), Waist-Hip Ratio.

Biochemical parameters: Fasting glucose, Fasting insulin, G120 (Glucose at 120 minutes), Vitamin D

Calculated Indices: HOMA-IR (Homeostatic Model Assessment for Insulin Resistance):

$$\text{HOMA-IR} = \frac{\text{Fasting Glucose}(mg/dl) * \text{Fasting Insulin}}{405}$$

$$\frac{G_0}{I_0} = \frac{\text{Fasting Glucose } (mg/dL)}{\text{Fasting Insulin}}$$

Statistical Analysis:

Descriptive Statistics: Mean, Standard Deviation (SD), Minimum and Maximum were calculated for continuous variables using the describe() function from the psych package (Wickham, 2014).

Correlation Analysis: Pearson's correlation was used to assess the relationship between metabolic parameters (Huang et al., 2022).

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2 (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

Multiple Linear Regression:

Multiple Linear Regression: A linear regression model was built to assess predictors of HOMA-IR, where fasting insulin, fasting glucose, BMI and WHR were independent variables (Hosmer & Lemeshow, 2000; Hastie et al., 2009).

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \dots \dots \dots + \beta_nx_n + \varepsilon$$

Where, β_0 is the intercept.

$\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ are the regression coefficients

ε is the error term

HOMA-IR is the dependent variable

Fasting insulin, Fasting Glucose, BMI and Waist-Hip Ratio are independent variables.

RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics

```
library(readxl)
data = read_xlsx("C:/Users/91954/Desktop/Insulin_data.xlsx")
head(data)
```

The descriptive statistics for the variables are presented below.

Variables	Mean \pm SD	Minimum	Maximum
Age	24.82 \pm 4.48	15.0	40.0
Height (cms)	152.84 \pm 6.82	141.0	170.0
Weight (kgs)	64.21 \pm 8.16	49.0	90.0
BMI	27.7 \pm 3.35	19.8	34.3
Waist (cms)	90.43 \pm 8.84	71.0	119.0
Hip (cms)	106.48 \pm 10.53	85.0	132.0
W-H RATIO	0.85 \pm 0.04	0.8	0.9
Vitamin d levels	14.81 \pm 3.94	8.3	25.3
Fasting insulin levels	24.29 \pm 7.45	8.3	41.0
Fasting glucose levels G0 MG/DL	92.9 \pm 8.39	72.0	120.0
G120	135.45 \pm 15.33	101.0	167.0
HOMA IR	5.59 \pm 1.85	1.8	9.3
G0/i0	4.25 \pm 1.57	2.2	10.4

Create boxplots for visualization

```

par(mfrow=c(2,4))
for(col in names(data)) {
  boxplot(data[[col]], main=col, col="lightblue")
}

```

Correlation Matrix for the variables:

```

cor_matrix = cor(data, method = 'pearson')
print(round(cor_matrix,3))

```

Variable 1	Variable 2	Pearson's Correlation	P Value
BMI	HOMA IR	0.223	0.026
Fasting Glucose	HOMA IR	0.389	0.005
W-H RATIO	Fasting Insulin	-0.152	0.131
Fasting Insulin	HOMA IR	0.961	0.001

```

corrplot(cor_matrix,
  method = "color",
  type = "upper",
  addCoef.col = "black",
  tl.col = "black",
  tl.srt = 50,
  number.cex = 1)

```


Correlation Analysis :

Correlation analysis was performed to assess relationships among key metabolic variables:

- i) BMI showed a Weak positive correlation with HOMA-IR ($r = 0.223$, $P = 0.026$), suggesting a minor association between body mass index and insulin resistance.
- ii) Fasting glucose and HOMA-IR exhibited a moderate positive correlation($r = 0.389$, $P = 0.05$), indicating that higher glucose levels are somewhat associated with increased insulin resistance.
- iii) Waist-Hip Ratio and fasting insulin levels showed no significant correlation ($r=0.152,P=0.13$) suggesting that central obesity may not be a direct predictor fasting insulin levels in this sample.
- iv) HOMA-IR showed a Strong positive correlation with fasting insulin ($r=0.961,P=0.001$), reinforcing its role as a key indicator of insulin resistance.

Regression Analysis:

MLR model: HOMA-IR as dependent, others as independent

```
mlr_model <- lm(`HOMA-IR` ~ . , data = data)
```

```
summary_mlr <- summary(mlr_model)
```

```
print(summary_mlr)
```

Predictor Variable	Coefficient	Standardized Beta	P Value	Interpretation
Intercept	-5.628	0.146	0.001	*
Fasting glucose levels G0 MG/DL	0.059	0.27	0.003	Significant Positive Predictor
Fasting insulin levels	0.229	0.927	0.001	Significant Positive Predictor
Age	0.006	0.003	0.015	Significant Positive Predictor
BMI	-0.002	-0.003	0.659	Not Significant
W-H RATIO	0.056	0.001	0.877	Not Significant

$$Y = -5.628 + (0.229 * \text{Fasting Insulin}) + (0.059 * \text{Fasting Glucose}) + (0.006 * \text{Age})$$

```
optimal_model = ols_step_both_p(mlr_model)
```

```
print(optimal_model)
```

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
1	0.908	0.824	0.819

A multiple linear regression model was applied to identify predictors of HOMA-IR. The model included fasting insulin, fasting glucose, BMI and waist-hip ratio as independent variables.

- i) The model has an R^2 value of 0.824, indicating that 82.4% of the variability in HOMA-IR is explained by the predictors.
- ii) Standardized beta coefficients:
 - a) Fasting Glucose: $\beta = 0.270$, $p = 0.003$
 - b) Fasting Insulin: $\beta = 0.927$, $p = 0.001$
 - c) BMI: $\beta = -0.003$, $p = 0.659$
 - d) Waist-Hip Ratio: $\beta = 0.001$, $p = 0.877$
 - e) Age : $\beta = 0.003$, $p = 0.015$

This suggest that fasting insulin and glucose significantly predict HOMA-IR, while BMI and W-H ratio were not statistically significant in this model.

DISCUSSION

The present study aimed to explore the relationship between insulin resistance (measured by HOMA-IR) and various metabolic parameters among young adults. The results revealed that fasting insulin and fasting glucose were strong predictors of HOMA-IR, which aligns with the biological understanding of insulin resistance (Matthews et al., 1985).

The strong positive correlation between fasting insulin and HOMA-IR ($r = 0.961$, $p < 0.001$) supports the calculation formula and highlights its clinical relevance (Kim et al., 2023). Fasting glucose also showed a moderate correlation ($r = 0.389$, $p = 0.005$), indicating a meaningful association (Rabari et al., 2022). BMI, although positively correlated with HOMA-IR ($r = 0.223$, $p = 0.026$), was not statistically significant in the regression model, suggesting a weaker predictive power (Midha et al., 2015).

Additionally, the waist-hip ratio showed no significant correlation with fasting insulin ($r = -0.152$, $p = 0.131$), implying that central obesity may not directly reflect insulin levels in this specific population (Zhu & Chen, 2015).

The multiple linear regression model ($R^2 = 0.824$) indicated excellent model fit and predictive accuracy. This suggests that a data-driven approach using standard regression techniques can effectively predict insulin resistance (James et al., 2013; Kuhn & Johnson, 2013).

The strength of this study lies in the application of statistical and data science methods, including correlation and regression analysis using R programming (Wickham, 2014; Beam & Kohane, 2018). This enhances transparency, reproducibility, and efficiency (Peng, 2015).

However, limitations include the cross-sectional study design, which may affect generalizability. Future studies may benefit from incorporating advanced data science techniques such as machine learning models to enhance prediction and classification accuracy (Chen & Asch, 2017; Miotto et al., 2018).

LIMITATIONS

This study is limited by its cross-sectional design, which precludes establishing causality. Additionally, important confounding factors such as gestational age, dietary patterns, physical activity and comorbid conditions were not recorded in this dataset. These unmeasured variables may have influenced the metabolic markers and insulin resistance levels. Future studies that follow participants over time and include these factors may help provide stronger and more generalizable conclusions.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that fasting insulin and fasting glucose levels are significant predictors of insulin resistance (HOMA-IR) among young adults. While BMI showed a weak association, waist-hip ratio did not significantly correlate with insulin levels, suggesting that not all anthropometric measures are strong predictors of insulin resistance.

The high R² value in the multiple linear regression model reflects that traditional statistical techniques, when combined with data science tools like R programming can effectively be used in medical research to predict key outcomes such as insulin resistance.

This study highlights the importance of early identification of metabolic risk using accessible variables and sets the stage for incorporating more advanced data science techniques in future research.

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